

Preparation of High Char-Yield Resins for
Carbon-Carbon Composites
S. L. Jwo, J. C. Chen, W. Y. Chen, S. E. Hsu
Chung Shan Institute of Science and Technology
Lungtan, Taiwan 32500, Republic of China

ABSTRACT

Phenolic resin synthesized by a aldehyde/phenol molar ratio of 1.3 : 1 with different catalysts has been studied. The synthesized phenolic resins were cured and then postcured under varied condition. After that the hardened resin was subjected to high-temperature carbonization. Effect of catalysts, and postcure condition on char yield were analyzed in order to get a high-char yield matrix precursor for making carbon-carbon composites (C/C composites). Experimental results showed that the catalyst type and postcure condition of phenolic resin might affect the final char yield significantly. High char yield can be obtained by postcuring with small increment of temperature up to 170 °C. For synthesized resin with NaOH or Na₂CO₃ catalyst, the highest char yield about 71.0% was found. Effect of cured polyimide under different postcured condition on char yield has also been studied and the results would also be discussed.

KEYWORDS: Char Yield; Matrix/Phenolic, Polyimide; Carbonization; Postcure; Carbon/Carbon Composites.

1. INTRODUCTION

Polymer matrix based carbon or graphite composites are usually chosen for preparation of C/C composites since it can form C/C skeletons after carbonization. A good matrix precursor should have high carbon char yields and maintain high percentage of mechanical properties after the resin or composites are carbonized. Two methods are commonly employed for preparation of C/C composites. Firstly, by chemical vapor deposition (CVD), and secondly, by liquid impregnation. Liquid impregnation method

usually causes the liquid resin shrinking when it is carbonized, resulting in residual stresses. However, it is still largely used to prepare C/C composites since it costs less and is better suited for thicker parts compared to CVD method. Generally, shrinkage of resin matrix reduced as the carbon char yield increased. Therefore, the resin with high char yield would facilitate to make high performance C/C composites(1). Pitch and thermosetting resins like phenolics, epoxy resins, etc., are commonly used as the carbon precursor in liquid impregnation. Among them, phenolic resin is most largely chosen as the carbon precursor for C/C skeletons(2, 3) since it costs less and has high char yield after carbonization at 1 atmosphere. Depending on the type of resin and postcuring condition employed(1, 4-7), different amount of char yield can be obtained during carbonization at 1000°C. For phenolic resin, it has been indicated(8, 9) that an optimum char yield can be obtained at a formaldehyde/phenol molar ratio (F/P) of 1.3:1. A series of phenolic resins were thus synthesized with F/P=1.3 molar ratio by varied catalysts. The synthesized phenolic resins were cured and then postcured under varied condition. After that the hardened resin was carbonized at 1000°C. Effects of catalyst and postcure condition on char yield were studied. Recently, a newly addition-type polyimide, designated as CSPI (Chang Shan modified Polyimide), has been developed(10). Better thermo-oxidation resistant properties were found compared to conventional polyimide, for example, PMR-15. It is interesting to make C/C composites by using this polymer composite. Effect of cured polyimide under different postcure condition on char yield has thus been studied.

2. EXPERIMENT PROCEDURE

2.1 Preparation of Phenolic Resins Suitable amount of reagent-grade phenol, 37% aqueous formalin (F/P=1.3), and ammonia water were mixed thoroughly and refluxed at 95~100°C for 1 hour. After cooling, it was then dehydrated to form phenolic resin (A). The resin was casted and cured at following condition: 60°C for 10 hr., 80°C for 10 hr., 100°C for 16 hr. and 120°C for 12 hr. After that it was then postcured by gradually increasing temperature. The postcure conditions are given in Table 1. Similarly, suitable amount of formalin and phenol with sodium hydroxide (NaOH), calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)₂), and sodium carbonate (Na₂CO₃) catalyst respectively were used to synthesize phenolic resin. Reaction condition is given in the following: 64~68°C for 3.5 hr., 74~78°C for 1 hr., and 82~84°C for 1 hr. After reaction was complete, the reaction mixture was cooled and a weak organic acid was introduced to neutralized the mixture. Then it was dehydrated to obtain the phenolic resin. The obtained resin with NaOH-catalyzed (B), Ca(OH)₂-catalyzed (C), and Na₂CO₃-catalyzed (D) were then casted and cured separately with following condition: 80°C for 36 hr., 100°C for 12 hr., and 120°C for 12 hr. The hardened resin were then postcured under varied conditions, as indicated in Table 1.

2.2 Preparation of Cured Polyimide Polyimide resins were prepared from dianhydride, anhydride with curable end group, and diamine by the procedure described by S. E. Hsu et. al.(10). After the resins were set, it was cured at 300°C 2 hr. The cured polyimide was then subjected to nitrogen atmosphere for postcure. The condition for postcure was indicated in Table 2. Weights of initial cure samples and final postcured samples were recorded.

2.3 Carbonization All the postcured samples were cut into 15mm(L) x 15mm(W) x 2.5mm(T) specimen. The specimen was then carbonized by gradually increasing temperature from ambient temperature to 1000°C, with the flowing nitrogen (200ml/min) passed through. Different heating rates were employed. After the temperature reached to 1000°C, it was held for 20 minutes at least, and then cooled.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Weight of postcured sample is used as a basis to calculate the char yield. Previous workers indicated(11, 12) that the phenolic resin postcured in air at atmosphere up to 220°C might cause oxidative degradation, which might result in continuous weight loss. In order to avoid the weight loss due to oxidative degradation, all the cured phenolic resins for this study were successively postcured in air from 130°C to 200°C in a reasonable time as shown in Table 3 to Table 6. It can be seen as the postcure temperature reaches to 170°C~200°C, the weight of phenolic resin becomes constant. It was assumed that at this stage no chemical crosslinking reaction occurred further, and therefore, the weight of phenolic resin of this stage was taken as the initial weight to calculate the char yield of it. For these resins which were carbonized before the postcure temperature reached to this point, the initial weight was taken as the same as the weight when the temperature reaches to 170°C~200°C theoretically. Figure 1 to Figure 4 showed the char yield results for the phenolic resin catalyzed with NaOH, Ca(OH)₂, Na₂CO₃ and NH₄OH, at different heating rate. It can be seen that at any postcure temperature, as the samples are carbonized, the char yield increases with decreasing heating rates. Figure 5 to Figure 7 also showed the char yield results of phenolic resin catalyzed with NaOH, Ca(OH)₂, Na₂CO₃ and NH₄OH. It can be seen that at the same heating rate during carbonization, the char yield changes slightly as the postcure temperature is increased. It is also shown that as the heating rate is over 20°C/hr, the apparent cracking is observed on the surface of the carbonized phenolic resin. Therefore, it is not possible to obtain even carbon char products if the heating rate is over 20°C/hr. For polyimide, weight decreases as the postcure temperature increases until it reaches to 390°C~420°C where the weight seems to remain constant, as shown in Table 7. At this stage, the weight of polyimide is taken as the initial weight to calculate the char yield. Table 8 shows the results. However, it seems unlikely that carbonization would not occur when the temperature

reached to 390°C~420°C. Therefore, char yields are also evaluated by using cured (unpostcured) sample weight as the initial weight to calculate. Figures 8 and 9 show the results, it can be seen that at high heating rate char yield increases with postcure temperature whereas at low heating rate char yield seems no change at all. It seems that at the lowest heating rate the highest char yield can be obtained although the difference of the char yield among the heating rate is not significant.

4. CONCLUSION

For phenolic resin, high char yield can be obtained as the heating rate is decreased. Better char yield can be obtained with Na₂CO₃ or NaOH catalyzed phenolic resins. For polyimide, at lowest heating rate (10°C/hr) the highest char yield is also observed although the difference is not significant compared with high heating rate. It seems that char yield from phenolic resin is better than that from polyimide. Although the char yield obtained from NaOH and Na₂CO₃ catalyzed phenolic resin is higher than that from NH₄OH catalyzed phenolic resin, the long-term high temperature oxidation behavior of these char are still not known. It is worth studying these effect in the future since the ion (Na⁺) exists in the char might affect the oxidation behavior of the char in the high temperature range.

5. REFERENCES

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6. BIOGRAPHY

Dr. S. E. Hsu, Director of MR&DC Center of Chung Shan Institute of Science and Technology (CSIST), obtained his Ph.D. degree from Stanford University in 1972. He has 30 years of research experience in the field of materials science. Dr. W. Y. Chen, Dr. J. C. Chen and Mr. S. L. Jwo are all research scientists in CSIST.

Table 1. Postcure schedule for cured phenolic resin

Postcure cycle: Successive time and temperature condition
 Cured sample \longrightarrow Postcured at 130°C for 12 hr. (XA1)*
 \longrightarrow 140°C for 6 hr. (XA2) \longrightarrow 150°C for 6 hr. (XA3)
 \longrightarrow 160°C for 6 hr. (XA4) \longrightarrow 170°C for 6 hr. (XA5)
 \longrightarrow 180°C for 3 hr. (XA6) \longrightarrow 200°C for 3 hr. (XA7)

*1. Marks (XA1, ..., XA7), respectively, stand for a sample which is postcured from the initial "cured sample" step to the step which is marked. For example, sample XA3 means sample is postcured at 130°C for 12 hr., 140°C for 6 hr., and 150°C for 6 hr.

*2. X=A, B, C or D, it stands for NH_4OH -catalyzed phenolic resin as X=A, and NaOH-catalyzed as X=B, $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ -catalyzed as X=C, and Na_2CO_3 -catalyzed as X=D.

Table 2. Postcure schedules for cured polyimide

Sample No.	Postcure step (in N_2 atmosphere)
1	320°C, 18 hr.
2	320°C, 2 hr. ; 340°C, 18hr.
3	320°C, 2 hr. ; 340°C, 2 hr. ; 360°C, 18 hr.
4	320°C, 2 hr. ; 340°C, 2 hr. ; 360°C, 2 hr. 390°C, 18 hr.
5	320°C, 2 hr. ; 340°C, 2 hr. ; 360°C, 2 hr. ; 390°C, 2 hr. ; 420°C, 18 hr.

Table. 3. Percentage of weight loss from cure to postcure for NH_4OH -catalyzed phenolic resin.

Sample mark	AA1	AA2	AA3	AA4	AA5	AA6	AA6
Weight loss(%)	8.3	9.0	8.9	9.0	9.0	9.0	9.0

Table. 4. Percentage of weight loss from cure to postcure for NaOH -catalyzed phenolic resin.

Sample mark	BA1	BA2	BA3	BA4	BA5	BA6	BA6
Weight loss(%)	5.2	8.2	8.7	9.6	10.1	10.5	10.2

Table. 5. Percentage of weight loss from cure to postcure for $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ -catalyzed phenolic resin.

Sample mark	CA1	CA2	CA3	CA4	CA5	CA6	CA6
Weight loss(%)	6.5	8.0	8.6	9.5	9.3	9.8	10.2

Table. 6. Percentage of weight loss from cure to postcure for Na_2CO_3 -catalyzed phenolic resin.

Sample mark	DA1	DA2	DA3	DA4	DA5	DA6	DA6
Weight loss(%)	8.4	9.2	10.2	10.7	11.2	11.0	11.2

Table. 7. Percentage of weight loss from cure to postcure for cured polyimide.

Sample No.	1	2	3	4	5
Weight loss(%)	2.3	3.0	5.1	11.3	11.4

Table. 8. Char yield from polyimide* (postcured sample weight as starting weight.)

Heating rate(°C/hr)	Carbon char weight, %				
	1	2	3	4	5
10	68.43	68.43	-	76.43	76.49
20	67.44	66.65	69.21	74.27	74.73
50	65.57	64.02	66.52	73.42	73.57
100	65.63	62.49	67.09	68.31	72.65
200	64.33	65.24	64.58	73.29	74.82
300	64.52	65.24	66.14	73.54	74.71

*. For all samples cracks are found on surface after carbonization.

Fig.1. Char yield at different heating rate for four kinds of phenolic resins under A1 step postcuring cycle.

Fig. 2. Char yield at different heating rates for four kinds of phenolic resins under A3 step postcuring cycle.

Fig. 3. Char yield at different heating rates for four kinds of phenolic resins under A5 step postcuring cycle.

Fig. 4. Char yield at different heating rates for four kinds of phenolic resins under A7 step postcuring cycle.

Fig. 5. Char yield at different postcuring steps for four kinds of phenolic resins under heating rate of 10 °C/hr.

Fig. 6. Char yield at different postcuring steps for four kinds of phenolic resins under heating rate of 50 °C/hr.

Fig. 7. Char yield at different postcuring steps for four kinds of phenolic resins under heating rate of 200 °C/hr.

Fig. 8. Char yield at different heating rates for polyimide resin under varied postcuring step.

Fig. 9. Char yield at different postcuring steps for polyimide resin under varied heating rate.